

netWorked Youth Research for Empowerment in the Digital society

Grant Agreement number: 727066

Platform v2

WP3_D3.3

V1.2

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1 Introduction

The WYRED project (netWorked Youth Research for Empowerment in the Digital society) (García-Peñalvo, 2016d, 2017; García-Peñalvo & Kearney, 2016) aims to provide a framework for research in which children and young people can express and explore their perspectives and interests in relation to digital society (García-Peñalvo, 2016b; Griffiths et al., 2017), but also a platform (Durán-Escudero, García-Peñalvo, & Therón-Sánchez, 2017; García-Peñalvo, 2016c; García-Peñalvo & Durán-Escudero, 2017), which represents a technological ecosystem for the project development (García-Holgado & García-Peñalvo, 2013, 2016, 2018a, 2018b; García-Peñalvo, 2016a, 2018; García-Peñalvo & García-Holgado, 2017).

This deliverable presents a summary of the status of the WYRED platform, where all the details about the architecture of the platform, the used technologies and the current functionalities can be found.

2 Technical report

In this section is described all platform information from the point of view of a developer.

2.1 Platform's architecture

The platform architecture has an important role in this project due to it is not a monolithic software because it has been created joining and adapting other developments. The main software used is Drupal a CMS (Content Management System), that it is the base for the platform. To achieve all WYRED requirements it has been installed some Drupal modules and it also has been developed some specific modules and the WYRED's theme.

At the moment, the platform uses two servers (Figure 1):

- A server with Drupal and its dependencies (LAMP).
- A server with Apereo CAS, MySQL and the WYRED API.

Figure 1. WYRED Platform architecture (García-Peñalvo, García-Holgado, Vázquez-Ingelmo, & Seoane-Pardo, 2018)

2.2 Platform technologies

•

Software	Type	Server	Use	Technologies
Drupal	CMS	A	WYRED Platform	PHP, HTML, CSS, LESS, JS, Drupal, Grunt
Apereo CAS	CAS	B	Single sign-on Manage users' private information	JAVA, Spring, SQL
MySQL	Database	B	Keep users' private information and inclusion data private	SQL
WYRED API	REST API	B	Access all information saved in the Database	PHP, Slim, SQL

Other technologies and skills have been also required:

- Git as version control system. It's linked with Redmine a project management tool.
- A large knowledge in systems administration: scripts, LAMP, Docker, Let's encrypt...

3 Results

The following section describes the main parts of the WYRED Platform with detailed captures of each view.

3.1 Registration

WYRED is a private community, for this reason in order to register, you have to get a personal invitation (Figure 2).

The screenshot shows the 'Create Invite by e-mail' form on the WYRED platform. The form is set against a dark header with navigation links: HOME, COMMUNITIES, PROJECTS, EVENTS, HELP, and USER ACCOUNT. The WYRED logo and tagline 'The platform for the young' are visible in the top left. The form fields include:

- E-mail ***: A text input field with a blue note: 'Type the e-mail address of the person you wish to invite. For children under 14 years you can use a false email account, after create the invitation you have to save the invitation link and give them to a child. Example: sweden2@wyredproject.eu'.
- Name ***: A text input field.
- Surname ***: A text input field.
- Date of birth ***: A date picker with a blue note: 'You cannot invite people minor than 7 years.' and an example: 'E.g., 16/06/2018'.
- Country ***: A dropdown menu with '- Select a value -'.
- Language ***: A dropdown menu with '- Select a value -' and a note: 'Default language for e-mails, and preferred language for site presentation.'
- Community**: A blue bar showing 'Test (471)' and a refresh icon.
- Send Invitation**: A button at the bottom of the form.

Figure 2. Personal invitation

With the invitation, a user can access to the registration page, where she will have to fill some fields to create his public and private profile and to configure how she wants to use the Platform (Figure 3).

WYRED

Items marked with an asterisk (*) are required fields.

Username *

Username should be unique, it is used to difference you from other users and maintenance your privacy. Spaces are not allowed; punctuation is not allowed except for periods, hyphens and underscores.

E-mail address *

A valid e-mail address. All e-mails from the system will be sent to this address. The e-mail address is not made public and will only be used if you wish to receive a new password or wish to receive certain news or notifications by e-mail.

Password *

Confirm password *

Provide a password for the new account in both fields.

Public data

These data will be visible for all users and they will help you to engage in the platform

Do you speak any of these languages *

- English
- Deutsch
- Español
- Türkçe
- Italiano
- עברית

Select all languages that you know

Private data

These data will keep hidden in the platform and only the administrator will be able to consult them

Name *

Surname *

Gender *

Male
 Female

Education level *

Year of Birth *

Terms of Use

I agree with these **Terms of Use ***

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[Terms of use](#)

Figure 3. Registration page

Highlight that the Platform is fully responsive, it can be used from different devices. Figure 4 shows an example of the registration form in a smartphone.

Figure 4. Registration page in a smartphone

3.2 Login

The login page (Figure 5) has links to the legal terms and to the help page with videos about how to use the Platform as an anonymous user and some training actions.

Figure 5. Login page

When a user clicks on the enter button, she is redirected to the CAS login page (Figure 6). After she introduces the username and password, she is redirected to the Platform.

Figure 6. CAS login page

After login (also after finishing the registration process), the user will see a welcome message, a link to the Welcome community and a message to complete the inclusion form (Figure 7).

Figure 7. Welcome page

Moreover, a feed with the activity in your communities in the last two weeks is available in the homepage. User can see the last post and threads published in the forums of your communities (Figure 8). Regarding the activity related to the research projects, last projects uploaded to the Platform in the public communities are visible in a block of the homepage.

Activity in your communities

Welcome

- **RESEARCH PROJECTS' FRIENDS IN EUROPE!!!**

Have you published a research or you are new to the platform?

- **La desigualdad en sus distintos aspectos desde una visión global**
I was looking for some public projects and i was reading some of them and when i saw the picture of the project that reminded me the current world especially about the men and women equality so i would like to read it in english. So im waiting for the english version .
- **ISLAM IS LOVE** New comment
I would like to underline that I am a Muslim person and also I highly mention that the cover of the project and the title of the project, they don't match. I think that the project can cause to think that the Muslim people are destroying the people.
- **About How Italy is seen by other countries project**
I have seen your project but 'cause of the language I could not read it. As I understood it's about other countries thoughts about Italy and Italian people. If it's possible I would like to read it in English. Thanks in advance.
- **Modern Technologies - and their Effects on Tourism Industry**
I like this article. Thank you for this text but can you send me the english version of the first page. Thanks again :)
- **Translation Request** 2 new comments
Is it possible for you to translate this text to English?

#metoo

WYRED
Platform

Last projects

Vittime di bullismo: la storia di chi in sé ha trovato la...

I giovani e il mondo del lavoro

Giovani, identità e politica: una storia alternativa

More projects

Power & Dominion of social media

Figure 8. Activity in the user communities

3.3 Help

The help page is also available for logged users but shows more videos related to the functionality available for young people and facilitators (Figure 9).

Figure 9. Help page

3.4 Take part in a community

The user can also see the available public communities in the page for the communities (Figure 10). This page is composed by three main parts: (1) information about the total number of communities and a set of tools to filter them; (2) a column with information of your own communities and the tools for facilitators (in case that the user has that role); (3) and a list of communities with the picture, title, description and language or languages used in the community.

Figure 10. Public communities page

The user can subscribe to all communities that she is interested in order to take part. When a user enters to a public community when she is not a member, she can see a link to subscribe or join to the community (Figure 11).

Figure 11. A community page when the user is not a member

Figure 12. A community page when the user is a member

When a user is member of a community, she can see more tools to interact and participate (Figure 12). In particular, the user has publication tools to create new events, forum threads or projects inside the community; notification tools to receive notifications of activity inside the community; and a link to unsubscribe.

Regarding the notifications, when a user becomes member of a community, the notifications are enabled by default for threads and events. The notification related to the comments in the forum threads are inside each thread, so a user can subscribe to the comments of a particular thread instead all of them. Moreover, when a user writes in a forum thread, the user is subscribed automatically to the comments notification of that thread.

Figure 13. A community page when the user is a facilitator of the community

On the other hand, when a user is facilitator in a community, there are more tools available for him. In particular, a block named “Administration” is enabled (Figure 13). The facilitator has tools for:

- Manage community members.
- Add registered users to the community. This is the only way to add members to a private community because is not visible in the communities list.
- Invite new users to register in the Platform and join to the community.
- Manage the forums structure (Figure 14).

Furthermore, the facilitator can subscribe to the notifications related to new members' subscriptions in the community.

Figure 14. Tool for managing forums structure inside a community

The members and facilitators can participate in the forum threads. The way to participate is to write a comment or post with text, pictures or attached files (Figure 15).

Figure 15. A forum thread where the user can participate

3.5 Research projects

Young people in each community will define and work in their own research projects. When they finish their projects, they will share in the Platform. The facilitators of the community will create these research projects inside the community in which have been developed.

There are a lot of information that can be shared about a project, most of them are visible for all users of the Platform by default. Highlight two elements in this form (Figure 16). First, the “Video on Youtube” field to publish videos automatically on the WYRED channel on Youtube. Second, a set of fields to share the results of the project, with a required field to configure the visibility of the result - only visible inside the community, visible for all users of the Platform, visible outside the Platform -.

Figure 16. Form to create and share research projects

All public project (facilitator can create private projects only visible in the community) are available in a page inside the Platform, the projects page (Figure 17). This page has two main parts, at the beginning information about the total number of projects and a set of filters to find and sort the

available projects. The second part is a set of thumbnails with the title and a brief description of the research projects.

Figure 17. Projects page

User can click in any of the projects and get detailed information about it. Figure 18 shows a real research project. Users inside the Platform can give 1 to 5 stars to the projects as a way to evaluate it.

Finally, the public projects are available through an RSS channel (<https://platform.wyredproject.eu/projects.xml>). This feed is used to embed the projects in the WYRED website and share them automatically on Facebook and Twitter profiles.

HOME
COMMUNITIES
PROJECTS
EVENTS ▾
HELP
USER ACCOUNT ▾

WYRED

The platform for the young

HOME » COMMUNITIES » NEW TECHNOLOGIES IN TOURISM » PROJECT » MODERN TECHNOLOGIES - AND THEIR EFFECTS ON TOURISM INDUSTRY

View
Edit

Modern Technologies - and their Effects on Tourism Industry

Our world is currently filled with modern technology due to the noteworthy progress scientists have made in recent years. Artificial intelligence and robotics have become significantly advanced and are commonly found in the modern working fields. The adoption of service automation is able to facilitate production, transportation, medicine, education, tourism, and many other areas. The question is whether or not the world of employment will benefit from this embrace of machinery and what challenges human employees might face if robots were to actively participate in various business departments.

As well Virtual reality can come in handy in many different fields and is believed to facilitate many tasks we have to face. In social sciences for example, VR is being used to study and replicate interactions of human beings in a controlled environment. Also, surgery training can nowadays be done through VR technologies. The benefits of an altered or artificial environment can be taken advantage of for educational or training purposes where individuals can develop skills without the pressure of failure and the fear of consequences which are constantly present in the real world. But virtual reality is also used for entertainment purposes, in public or privately. This includes gaming, 3D cinema or roller coasters that are offering an extraordinary experience by using modern technologies.

Further, it is no longer the question if algorithms influence our decisions regarding touristic attractions but more, how they work and how they influence our decision and actions. These developments tend to a challenge for traditional travel agencies, as booking can be done quickly, easy and all in all more effective.

Tags: digital society | technology |

Language: English
German (Deutsch)

Vote: Your rating: None Average: 5 (2 votes)

Objectives

Analysis of the new technologies (list), which are relevant for the tourism industry

Results

 [modern technologies and their effects on tourism industry.pdf](#)
The authors identify three forms of modern technology impacting the tourism industry: Virtual Reality, Algorithms, and Robotics and briefly explain their effects.

Community

You can join to **New Technologies In Tourism** to speak in English, German (Deutsch) about the project

Or enter to the **Welcome community** to comment about this project in English

Participants

[neumannblanca](#)
[lisa.birett](#)
[All_gator](#)

Figure 18. Project details

3.6 Events

Inside each community, the members can create events related to the community. These events are available in a calendar inside the community and also in a global calendar in the events page (Figure 19). Furthermore, the facilitators can create new events for all users in the community with the “New event” tool.

The screenshot shows the WYRED Events page. At the top, there is a navigation bar with links for HOME, COMMUNITIES, PROJECTS, EVENTS (selected), and HELP. A user account dropdown is visible on the right. Below the navigation bar is a header with the WYRED logo and the tagline "The platform for the young". A breadcrumb trail shows "HOME » EVENTS".

The main content area features a calendar for November 2017. The calendar is a grid with days of the week (Mon to Sun) and dates. Several events are listed in orange boxes:

- Wednesday, 8th: Eggenburg Explorations
- Thursday, 9th: Doga Testing of the platform
- Friday, 10th: Getting Started
- Friday, 11th: Young people talking at the Instill conference
- Wednesday, 15th: Partners test

Navigation controls for the calendar include "Prev" and "Next" buttons. To the right of the calendar, there are four circular buttons for "Month" (05), "Week" (20), "Day" (16), and "Year" (18). Below these are two main sections:

- Publish events**: A blue box containing a "New event" button with a pencil icon.
- Your communities**: A blue box containing three icons: "Test" (people icon), "Welcome" (landscape icon), and "Technical support - WYRED Platform" (question mark icon).

Figure 19. Events page

3.7 User's profile

Finally, each user has a personal page his own public information inside the Platform (Figure 20).

Figure 20. The user's profile

The user has also access to the inclusion form in order to improve and study about the diversity in the WYRED context (Figure 21). The inclusion form is not mandatory, but all users see a warning message until they complete it.

The answers of the inclusion form are saved outside the Platform, in a different database, as a secure measure.

Finally, the user with a facilitator role can manage the invitations sent by her (Figure 22). She can find a link to this tool in his profile. Each facilitator can see the accepted invitations (this means that the user finished the registration process), the pending invitations (the user can still use the invitation link to finish the registration), the expired invitations (the invitation link expires after one month) and a form to send invitations without join the new user to a specific community, only to the Welcome community by default. Regarding the expired invitations, the facilitator can delete them in order to send them again (Figure 23).

HOME COMMUNITIES PROJECTS EVENTS ▾ HELP USER ACCOUNT ▾

WYRED

The platform for the young

Inclusion form

Dear participant,

in empowering children and young people to get heard in the digital society, a core aim of the WYRED project is to include a broad range of different voices, ideas and opinions into the project. We regard diverse perspectives to be a most valuable resource in dealing with (future) societal changes or digital developments. Therefore, in the following we ask you to answer some questions which focus on diversity and inclusion.

Questions marked with asterisk (*) are required fields.

Educational or work background

What is your highest level of education? *

- Select -

At the moment are you student in formal education? *

- Select -

If you are no student in formal education: What are you doing in the moment?

No answer

Socio-economic status

What is the highest school level attained by your mother? *

- Select -

What is the highest school level attained by your father? *

- Select -

Geographic location

Where do you live? *

- Select -

Where do you study or work? *

- Select -

Migration

Which language is mainly spoken in your family? *

- Select -

Where were you born? *

- Select -

Where was your father born? *

- Select -

Where was your mother born? *

- Select -

Ethnic background

Figure 21. Inclusion form

HOME COMMUNITIES PROJECTS EVENTS ▾ HELP USER ACCOUNT ▾				
WYRED The platform for the young				
ADMIN » EXPIRED » INVITATION				
View Edit Invitation				
Accepted Pending Expired Invite by e-mail				
Date created	Name	E-mail	Joined	Active
26/02/2018 - 11:35	Julia_@univie.ac	julia.univie.ac@univie.ac	Mon, 26/02/2018 - 11:53	Active
25/01/2018 - 23:20	gromed	gromed@protonmail.com	Sat, 27/01/2018 - 18:15	Active
16/01/2018 - 20:53	Elisa	elisa.serafini@univie.ac	Thu, 18/01/2018 - 23:56	Active
16/01/2018 - 20:53	anna.kobler	anna.kobler@univie.ac	Wed, 17/01/2018 - 13:30	Active
16/01/2018 - 20:53	Felix	felix.wittig@univie.ac	Tue, 23/01/2018 - 22:01	Active
16/01/2018 - 20:52	matthias.k.	matthias.koenig@univie.ac	Wed, 17/01/2018 - 16:37	Active
16/01/2018 - 20:52	stephan.k.	stephan.koenig@univie.ac	Wed, 17/01/2018 - 14:12	Active
16/01/2018 - 20:51	anna	anna.wittig@univie.ac	Tue, 23/01/2018 - 22:02	Active
16/01/2018 - 20:49	Julia	julia.univie@univie.ac	Wed, 17/01/2018 - 21:50	Active
16/01/2018 - 20:49	Mary	mary.muller@univie.ac	Wed, 17/01/2018 - 12:44	Active
16/01/2018 - 20:48	anna	anna.wittig@univie.ac	Wed, 24/01/2018 - 17:24	Active

Figure 22. Accepted invitations

HOME COMMUNITIES PROJECTS EVENTS ▾ HELP USER ACCOUNT ▾				
WYRED The platform for the young				
ADMIN » INVITATION » EXPIRED » EXPIRED				
View Edit Invitation				
Accepted Pending Expired Invite by e-mail				
Operations				
Delete item				
<input type="checkbox"/>	Date created	E-mail	Status	
<input type="checkbox"/>	16/01/2018 - 20:51	anna.wittig@univie.ac	Expired	
<input type="checkbox"/>	16/01/2018 - 20:50	gromed@protonmail.com	Expired	
<input type="checkbox"/>	16/01/2018 - 20:50	matthias.koenig@univie.ac	Expired	
<input type="checkbox"/>	16/01/2018 - 20:48	stephan.koenig@univie.ac	Expired	
<input type="checkbox"/>	16/01/2018 - 20:47	anna.wittig@univie.ac	Expired	
<input type="checkbox"/>	16/01/2018 - 20:47	anna.wittig@univie.ac	Expired	
<input type="checkbox"/>	16/01/2018 - 20:47	anna.wittig@univie.ac	Expired	

Figure 23. Expired invitations

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